

Fault tolerant control for DFIG wind turbine controlled by ADRC and optimized by genetic algorithm

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ABSTRACT

This research work deals with the modelling, control and simulation of a wind turbine based on the doubly fed induction generator (DFIG) in the current sensor's failure event. We present in the first time the model of the wind energy conversion system based on the DFIG and the control by active disturbances rejection control (ADRC) optimized by genetic algorithm. Particular focus is directed towards on a technique for detection, identification, isolation and reconfiguration of current sensor signals after failure. The combination of the two preceding techniques makes it possible to have a fault tolerant control to sensor faults which ensures continuity of service in all circumstances. The robustness of the proposed technique is tested under the MATLAB/Simulink environment.

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NOMENCLATURE

Φ_{rdq} : Rotor fluxes

V_{sdq} : Stator voltages dq axis

V_{rdq} : Rotor voltages dq axis

i_{sdq} : Stator currents dq axis

i_{rdq} : Rotor currents dq axis

ω_s : Rotor angular frequency

ω_r : Stator angular frequency

Φ_{rdq} : Rotor fluxes

1. INTRODUCTION

A real system during its operation can be impacted by faults, which generates a deviation from its normal operation and can cause its instability depending on the fault severity [1]. The variable speed electric drives that exist in wind power generation systems are equipped with sensors either for their protection or for their control [1]. In doubly fed induction generator (DFIG) based wind energy conversion systems, we often find current sensors for the stator and rotor currents, a voltage sensor for measuring the DC link voltage and optionally a speed or position sensor depending on the performance level required by the control method used [1], [2].

The performance level of the DFIG control relies particularly on the quality and accuracy of the feedback signal from the sensors. However, sensors can be weak links in the control loop [3]. The sensor fault would cause a malfunction of the control and lead in most cases to the system shutdown and the wind turbine disconnection.

Nevertheless, a shutdown results in a shutdown of the production system and therefore in a loss of an electrical energy quantity. This is more impacting as the requirements of electric grid managers are greater [4]. So, the development of a fault tolerant control therefore becomes more and more necessary and inevitable.

The DFIG control based on the active disturbances rejection control (ADRC), unlike other control techniques, makes it possible to compensate, in real time, internal and external disturbances, in particular those linked to the controller's sensitivity to parameters' variations of the generator [5]. This control technique has proven its effectiveness and robustness in several works but it requires reliable and precise measurement of rotor and stator currents to guarantee the wind system stability and precision. However, it does not take into account the sensors' faults which must be treated separately [1], [2].

Several works have dealt with the detection and isolation of sensor faults to improve the DFIG control robustness to the current sensors failure as well as increasing the quality of the electrical energy produced. The proposed method by Rothenhagen and Fuchsin [6] is based on an bilinear observer current to generate necessary residuals for the detection and reconfiguration of the current signals after one of the current sensors' failure. The disadvantage of this method is that the observer synthesis is based on the output currents of the same faulty sensor, which can make the values generated by the observer also erroneous and sensitive to the faulty sensor.

Gálvez-Carrillo and M. Kinnaert [7] have dealt with fault detection and isolation in current and voltage sensors of doubly-fed induction generators. The presented approach in this work for the fault's detection requires more time and entails many difficulties to have a fault tolerant control practically. The studies deal only with the case of a serious fault for the sensors in the DFIG. The work presented in [8] deals with fault-tolerant control of sensors using a Luenberger observer for the current's estimation. The control assumes a fixed wind speed.

In this work, we propose an active control based on ADRC optimized by genetic algorithm to control the active and reactive powers of DFIG, combined with a fault tolerant control which allows to compensate different types of current sensor faults, including gain, offset and open circuit faults for a variable wind speed. It is based on a current's estimator using a nonlinear model representation of the DFIG, by using only voltage signals as inputs. The estimated currents will be compared to the currents measured by the sensors and then fed into an algorithm for fault isolation and signal reconfiguration. We also interested in the robustness test of the proposed control, integrating the block of the rotor current sensor fault diagnostic under a variable wind profile, in the case of a fault impacting the gain, the offset and of the open circuit type.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. DFIG modeling

The DFIG model is obtained from the dynamic equations of stator and rotor fluxes (1) and voltages (2) in the dq reference [9], [10]:

$$\begin{cases} \Phi_{sd} = L_s i_{sd} + L_m i_{rd} \\ \Phi_{sq} = L_s i_{sq} + L_m i_{rq} \\ \Phi_{rd} = L_r i_{rd} + L_m i_{sd} \\ \Phi_{rq} = L_r i_{rq} + L_m i_{sq} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{cases} V_{sd} = R_s i_{sd} + \frac{d\Phi_{sd}}{dt} - \omega_s \Phi_{sq} \\ V_{sq} = R_s i_{sq} + \frac{d\Phi_{sq}}{dt} + \omega_s \Phi_{sd} \\ V_{rd} = R_r i_{rd} + \frac{d\Phi_{rd}}{dt} - \omega_r \Phi_{rq} \\ V_{rq} = R_r i_{rq} + \frac{d\Phi_{rq}}{dt} + \omega_r \Phi_{rd} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The structure of wind power system based on DFIG is presented in Figure 1. In this block diagram, the DFIG stator is directly connected to the grid and the rotor is connected to the grid through two converters, rotor side converter (RSC) and grid side converter (GSC), and a DC link. Usually, the RSC controls the produced powers, and the GSC controls the DC link voltage [9], [11], [12].

2.2. Active disturbances rejection control

Active disturbances rejection control is a robust control that improves system performances in the presence of disturbances. It is based on the extension of the model system by the use of an extended state observer (ESO) to estimate and cancel, in real time, internal and external disturbances. Figure 2 show the basic structure of ADRC controller [5], [13], [14].

Figure 1. Structure of wind power system based on DFIG

Figure 2. Structure of the ADRC controller

The f represents the total disturbances affecting the controlled quantities on the d and q axes, u is the control input of the loops [13]. b_0 is the known part of the generator parameters and K_p represent the ADRC controller gain [13].

2.2.1. Rotor side converter control

The form of the dynamic equations of stator and rotor currents and voltages, rotor currents expressions can be expressed to be (3) and (4) [13], [15]:

$$\frac{di_{rd}}{dt} = -\frac{R_r}{\sigma L_r} i_{rd} + \omega_r \cdot i_{rq} + \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} V_{rd} \tag{3}$$

$$\frac{di_{rq}}{dt} = -\frac{R_r}{\sigma L_r} i_{rq} - \omega_r \cdot i_{rd} - \omega_r \frac{L_m}{\sigma L_r L_s} \Phi_s + \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} V_{rq} \tag{4}$$

$\sigma = 1 - \frac{L_m^2}{L_s L_r}$ represent the dispersion coefficient. We can also put these equations as follows:

$$\frac{di_{rd}}{dt} = f_d(i_{rd}, d, t) + b_0 u(t) \tag{5}$$

$$\frac{di_{rq}}{dt} = f_q(i_{rq}, d, t) + b_0 u(t) \tag{6}$$

where:

$$\begin{cases} f_d = -\frac{R_r}{\sigma L_r} i_{rd} + \omega_r \cdot i_{rq} + (\frac{1}{\sigma L_r} - b_0) V_{rd} \\ u = V_{rd} , b_0 = \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

$$\begin{cases} f_q = -\frac{R_r}{\sigma L_r} i_{rq} - \omega_r \cdot i_{rd} - \omega_r \frac{L_m}{\sigma L_r L_s} \Phi_s + (\frac{1}{\sigma L_r} - b_0) V_{rq} \\ u = V_{rq} , b_0 = \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

2.2.2. Grid side converter control

The grid filter currents i_{fd} and i_{fq} are given by the following expressions [13], [16], [17]:

$$\frac{di_{fd}}{dt} = \frac{1}{L_f} V_{sd} - \frac{R_f}{L_f} i_{fd} - \omega_s i_{fq} - \frac{1}{L_f} V_{fd} \tag{9}$$

$$\frac{di_{fq}}{dt} = \frac{1}{L_f} V_{sq} - \frac{R_f}{L_f} i_{fq} - \omega_s i_{fd} - \frac{1}{L_f} V_{fq} \tag{10}$$

According to the ADRC structure, these expressions can be rearranged to be in the (11) and (12):

$$\frac{di_{fd}}{dt} = f_{fd}(i_{fd}, d, t) + b_0 u(t) \tag{11}$$

$$\frac{di_{fq}}{dt} = f_{fq}(i_{fq}, d, t) + b_0 u(t) \tag{12}$$

where:

$$\begin{cases} f_{fd} = \frac{1}{L_f} V_{sd} - \frac{R_f}{L_f} i_{fd} - \omega_s i_{fq} + (\frac{1}{L_f} - b_0) V_{fd} \\ u = V_{fd} , \quad b_0 = -\frac{1}{L_f} \end{cases} \tag{13}$$

$$\begin{cases} f_{fq} = \frac{1}{L_f} V_{sq} - \frac{R_f}{L_f} i_{fq} - \omega_s i_{fd} + (\frac{1}{L_f} - b_0) V_{fq} \\ u = V_{fq} , \quad b_0 = -\frac{1}{L_f} \end{cases} \tag{14}$$

The i_{fq} and i_{fd} currents are controlled to have a unity power coefficient. The block diagram of the RSC and GSC control is given in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Block diagram of the RSC and GSC control

2.3. Fault tolerant control

For ADRC-based DFIG control, it is often necessary to measure the stator current and rotor current and voltage. So, for current measurement, we can use either three sensors, one for each phase, or only two sensors and calculate the third of the two acquired signals, since the sum of the three currents is zero for a balanced three-phase system [18]–[20].

The Figure 4 shows the synoptic diagram of the rotor side converter control using ADRC integrating the detecting and reconfiguration block for sensor’s signals in the faults event. We will detail in the following section the usefulness and operation of each block of the preceding synoptic diagram for currents estimation, detection, isolation and reconfiguration of the signals at the appearance of rotor current faults.

2.3.1. Fault detection

This operation makes it possible to decide whether the system is or is not in a normal operating state. For this, a logic operation is performed, the response of this bloc must be binary (0 if there is no fault and 1 if the system is faulty). The technique is based on the fact that the phases sum of the balanced three-phase system is close to zero [18], [21]. The system is therefore faulty if this sum is greater than a threshold, which will be fixed during simulation, (output at 1) and in normal operation in the other case (output at 0). In Figure 5 we present the fault detection diagram.

Figure 4. Synoptic scheme of detection, identification, and reconfiguration block

Figure 5. Rotor and stator currents estimation block

2.3.2. Current estimation

The estimation of the stator and rotor currents is based on the measurement of the generator voltages. According to the mathematical equations of the DFIG modelling (voltage and flux), we can write the simplified equations of the DFIG dynamics in the following form (15) [21]–[24]:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1 = \frac{R_s}{\sigma L_s} x_1 + \left(\omega_s + \frac{L_m^2 \omega}{\sigma L_s L_r}\right) x_2 + \frac{R_r L_m}{\sigma L_s L_r} x_3 + \frac{L_m \omega}{\sigma L_s} x_4 + \frac{1}{\sigma L_s} u_1 - \frac{L_m}{\sigma L_s L_r} u_3 \\ \dot{x}_2 = -\left(\omega_s + \frac{L_m^2 \omega}{\sigma L_s L_r}\right) x_1 - \frac{R_s}{\sigma L_s} x_2 - \frac{L_m \omega}{\sigma L_s} x_3 + \frac{R_r L_m}{\sigma L_s L_r} x_4 + \frac{1}{\sigma L_s} u_2 - \frac{L_m}{\sigma L_s L_r} u_4 \\ \dot{x}_3 = -\frac{R_s L_m}{\sigma L_s L_r} x_1 - \frac{L_m \omega}{\sigma L_r} x_2 + \frac{R_r}{\sigma L_r} x_3 + \left(\omega_s - \frac{\omega}{\sigma}\right) x_4 - \frac{L_m}{\sigma L_s L_r} u_1 - \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} u_3 \\ \dot{x}_4 = \frac{L_m \omega}{\sigma L_r} x_1 + \frac{R_s L_m}{\sigma L_s L_r} x_2 - \left(\omega_s - \frac{\omega}{\sigma}\right) x_3 - \frac{R_r}{\sigma L_r} x_4 + \frac{L_m}{\sigma L_s L_r} u_2 + \frac{1}{\sigma L_r} u_4 \end{cases} \tag{15}$$

where:

$$x^T = (x_1 x_2 x_3 x_4)^T = (i_{sd} i_{sq} i_{rd} i_{rq})^T$$

$$u^T = (u_1 u_2 u_3 u_4)^T = (v_{sd} v_{sq} v_{rd} v_{rq})^T$$

The stator voltages are measured by a voltage sensor, and the rotor voltages are obtained directly from the ADRC control blocks presented in the previous section. The Figure 5 summarizes the method used to estimate the stator and rotor currents.

2.3.3. Identification of defective sensors

The identification of the defective sensor is done in two steps: i) Calculation of the difference between the estimated values $i_{rabc\ est}$ and the measured ones $i_{rabc\ meas}$ by the current sensors; and ii) Comparison of this deviation with a threshold to be set during the simulation.

The faulty sensor is identified as follows: If the value of the difference between the estimated value and the measured one is greater than the threshold, the sensor is considered defective and the output variable of the identification block is at logic state 1, otherwise it is at 0. The Figure 6 summarizes the method used to detect the sensor current fault and the fault identification diagram. The threshold must be greater than the maximum difference between the estimated value of the current and the measured one in the normal case without fault. This threshold depends on the precision of the current’s estimation method.

Figure 6. Faulty sensor detection block

2.3.4. Isolation and reconfiguration algorithm

In this part we are interested in the algorithm used for the generation of the currents to be transmitted to the ADRC controllers. For this, we have three cases to treat:

- If all the logic outputs of the detection block are at zero (no fault), the measured values of the currents $i_{rabc\ meas}$ are transmitted directly to the ADRC controllers.
- If only one sensor is faulty, its signal is isolated and reconfigured from the other two sensors (for example $i_{ra\ rec} = -i_{rb\ m} - i_{rc\ m}$ if sensor a is faulty).
- If two or three sensors are defective, the ADRC controllers will receive the generated currents by the estimation block in Figure 5.

Figure 7 summarize the isolation and reconfiguration algorithm presented previously.

Figure 7. Isolation and reconfiguration diagram

2.4. Optimization by genetic algorithm

The genetic algorithm is an optimization method based on theories of natural selection [25]. This technique is recognized to be very effective and efficient in finding optimal solutions to optimization problems.

It makes it possible to avoid local minima constituting a major problem in the case of nonlinear systems [25]–[27]. In this technique, the solutions to an optimization problem are represented as chromosomes from an initial population to evolve to an optimal solution [26]. This algorithm is based on three stages: selection, crossing and mutation. These three steps are used to have new individuals and subsequently assess their performance against the previous ones using a fitness function [26]. The optimal solution is represented the best individuals, this algorithm must be realized for many generations and finally stops when it reaches these chromosomes [25], [27].

In this research paper, genetic algorithm is used to optimize the DFIG control in the current sensor fault event. It is used to adjust the parameters K_p , β_1 and β_2 for extended state observer so as to obtain the optimal performance in terms of dynamics, robustness and disturbance rejection. The objective function is chosen so that the difference between the reference of active and reactive power and the measured one is as small as possible. The electromagnetic torque produced by DFIG and active stator power are proportional to the rotor current of q-axis. The reactive power is related to current rotor d-axis by a constant imposed by the grid. The (16) and (17) give the expressions of these reference currents:

$$i_{rdref} = \frac{\phi_s}{L_m} - \frac{L_s}{v_{sq}L_m} Q_{sref} \tag{16}$$

$$i_{rqref} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{L_s}{pL_m\phi_s} T_{emref} \tag{17}$$

A GA based ADRC optimization block for rotor current’s control can be represented in Figure 8. The types of the GA operations used are presented in Table 1. The genetic algorithm parameters used in this work are presented in Table 2. In Figure 9, we present the ADRC parameters’ evolution through the generation. From Figure 9, we can deduce the ARDC controller parameters K_p , β_1 and β_2 which are given in the Table 3.

Table 1. Types of the GA operations used

Property	Type
Selection	GA default selection function
Mutation	Uniformed
Crossover	Arithmetic

Table 2. Genetic algorithm parameters

Property	Value	Property	Value
Variables to optimize	3	Mutation fraction	0.01
Population size	50	Crossover fraction	0.08
Maximum size of generations	500	Tolerance	$5 \cdot 10^{-2}$

Table 3. ADRC Controller Parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Value obtained by GA	Lower range	Upper range
Currents controller gain (ADRC)	K_p	18680	1.0	20000
Extended state observer gains	β_1	4524.2	1.0	5000
	β_2	480900	1.0	500000

Figure 8. GA based ADRC optimization block

Figure 9. GA parameters’ evolution

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The parameters of a 1.5 MW DFIG, RL filter and the DC link parameters used in the simulation are presented in Tables 4 and 5. Simulation results are divided in two parts, first one tracking and control test, second one verifies fault tolerant control performance. In this research paper, the wind speed profile used is modelled by a sum of several harmonics, around an average speed of 8 m/s. We present in Figure 10 the used wind profile.

Table 4. DFIG parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Parameter	Symbol	Value
Rated power	P_s	1.5 M	Mutual cyclic inductance	L_m	13.5 mH
Stator resistance	R_s	8.9 m Ω	Number of pole pairs	p	2
Rotor resistance	R_r	13.7 m Ω	Optimal tip speed ratio	λ_{opt}	8.1
Stator inductance	L_s	13.7 mH	Maximal power coefficient	C_{pmax}	0.48
Rotor inductance	L_r	13.67 mH			

Table 5. Parameters of the RL Filter and the DC Link

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Filter resistance	R_f	0.25 Ω
Filter inductance	L_f	0.005 H
DC link Capacitor	C	0.0044 F
DC link voltage	U_{dc}	1200 V

3.1. Tracking and control test

As results of tracking and control test Figure 10 shows the simulation result for the active and reactive powers P and Q and the rotor current i_{rabc} of the DFIG, controlled by ADRC without rotor current sensor faults. The reference reactive power is initially chosen equal to 0 VAR to guarantee a unity power factor at the point of connection to the grid.

From Figure 10, the active and reactive powers controlled by ADRC and optimized by genetic algorithm, follow perfectly their references, and the rotor current frequency follow the wind profile considered for this simulation according to the DFIG rotation speed which further demonstrates the effectiveness of the ADRC command used.

Figure 10. Active and reactive power

3.2. Simulation of fault tolerant control performance

In this section, the performance of the DFIG control by ADRC will be tested with the rotor current estimator in the presence of current sensor faults. The objective is to validate the fault-tolerant control method. For this, we consider two scenarios which will be studied: i) An open circuit fault affecting only phase a between 4s and 6s; and ii) A gain fault of 0.5s applied to phase c between 2.5s and 4.5s, simultaneously with an offset fault affecting phase b between 5.5s and 7s.

According to the reference tracking test validated in the previous part, the system response always passes through a transient state before the steady state is established. This transient state (about 500 ms) causes also a transient state in the currents generated by the rotor current estimator, which is based on the rotor voltages generated by the ADRC controllers. Therefore, the proposed command remains always valid for faults appearing after starting the generator.

In Figure 11, we show the outputs of the residual's calculation block between the measured currents and the estimated currents, and the indicators of the sensor's current faults, obtained during the simulation under the wind speed variations. From this figure, the residual for the current i_{ra} (left figure) is different to zero due to the presence of the open circuit fault on the sensor a. the fault indicator also changes to 1. In the figure

on the right, the presence of gain and offset faults generates non-zero values in the residuals R_{rb} and R_{rc} and the indicators C_{rb} and C_{rc} changes to 1.

Figure 11. Residuals of rotor current

When all the sensors are in normal operation (indicated by a low state on the Delta outputs of the detection block), the FTC command returns the measured currents to the ADRC controllers. When a fault appears, the identification and reconfiguration block is used to generate the current $i_{rabc\text{ftc}}$. This current is equal either to the reconfigured current if the fault affects a single sensor or estimated one if several sensors are affected. During the start-up regime of the DFIG, the ADRC control block receives the measured current by the sensors.

Figure 12 shows the simulation results obtained for the rotor current in the case of the two scenarios taken as an example. It can be noted, according to this figure, that the first fault (OC open circuit) is applied only to phase a at 4s (i_{ra}). The current detection, estimation and reconfiguration block reacts instantly to isolate the fault and generate the rotor currents. It can be seen from these results that these generated currents are perfectly sinusoidal and conform to the magnitudes without defects (measured current i_{rabc} without fault). We note the same remark for the case of gain and offset fault applied simultaneously at 2.5s and 5.5s.

Figure 12. Rotors current with OC fault, offset fault and gain fault

For the active and reactive power P and Q , we can note, according to Figure 13, a strong divergence of these powers with more oscillations in the case of the sensor defect appearance with the conventional method, which does not integrate the reconfiguration technique (P_{conv} and Q_{conv}). However, the control of these powers by ADRC strategy, integrating the detection and reconfiguration technique of the current sensors signals, P_{ftc} and Q_{ftc} , presents better performances in terms of robustness, speed and monitoring of the reference values P_{ref} and Q_{ref} . This is valid for the three default scenarios considered.

Figure 13. Active and reactive power for OC, offset and gain fault

4. CONCLUSION

This article has dealt with the fault-tolerant control of DFIG current sensors, based on the ADRC technique optimized by genetic algorithm. This method consists of detecting and identifying faults in current sensors, estimating currents and reconfiguring sensor signals. In this work, we considered three types of faults: open circuit fault, offset and gain faults affecting the rotor current sensors. The simulation results obtained showed that the conventional control without a detection faults and signals reconfiguration strategy does not allow the wind energy conversion system, based on DFIG, to ensure the continuity of service in the event of current sensor failure. However, the proposed control makes it possible to detect the faults, identify the faulty current sensor, generate the estimated currents based only on the DFIG voltages and then isolate and reconfigure the signals for the erroneous sensors. The use of the genetic algorithm allowed us to have an optimal solution for the parameters' values of the ADRC controllers. As perspectives, this work can be further improved by considering a robust adaptive observer, based on the genetic algorithm, for rotor and stator currents estimation instead of the state estimator.

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